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VR 1.0
PT J
AU Linder, N
Giusti, M
Samuelsson, K
Barthel, S
AF Linder, Noah
Giusti, Matteo
Samuelsson, Karl
Barthel, Stephan
TI Pro-environmental habits: An underexplored research agenda in
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OI barthel, stephan/0000-0003-2637-2024; Giusti,
Matteo/0000-0003-0179-2540; Linder, Noah/0000-0003-4486-3644
SN 0044-7447
EI 1654-7209
PD MAR
PY 2022
VL 51
IS 3
BP 546
EP 556
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AF Gill, Abid Rashid
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TI Implementing and sustaining dietary change in the context of
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OI Axon, Stephen/0000-0003-1166-6118
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OI Lund, Thomas B/0000-0001-5282-1562; Hielkema,
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OI Jansson-Boyd, Cathrine/0000-0002-0644-6041
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Charlebois, Sylvain
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Li, Elton
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OI Dang, Hoa Le/0000-0002-5943-9515; Bruwer, Johan/0000-0001-7568-605X
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Pamucar, D
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S0 SUSTAINABILITY
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Meszaros, E
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Bucea-Manea-Tonis, R

Basic, J

Coelho, AS

Simion, VE

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Bucea-Manea-Tonis, Roczana

Basic, Jasmina

Coelho, Ana Sofia

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0000-0003-2708-1325;

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AR 7186

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TI Solving barrier ranking in clean energy adoption: An MCDM
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TI It's the mobility culture, stupid! Winter conditions strongly
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PD NOV
PY 2020
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AF Hugo, Andreza de Aguiar
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Perspectives of young Brazilians on circular economy
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OI Lima, Renato da Silva/0000-0002-5824-6607; de Aguiar Hugo,
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AF Malatesta, Troy
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Breadsell, Jessica K.
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Kristl, Z
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Salaj, Alenka Temeljotov
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Sallay, A
AF Szabo, Zita
Prohaszka, Viola
Sallay, Agnes
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S0 LAND
OI Sallay, Agnes/0000-0002-9250-3910
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AR 682
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Parlesak, A
Lindroos, AK
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AF Eustachio Colombo, Patricia
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Andermo, Susanne
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Susanne/ABE-2729-2020; Parlesak, Alexandr/K-6310-2013; Lindroos,
Anna
Karin/AGG-8362-2022; Patterson, Emma/H-5080-2019; Colombo,
Patricia
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OI Colombo, Patricia Eustachio/0000-0002-8505-116X; Parlesak,
Alexandr/0000-0002-8973-3467; Patterson, Emma/
0000-0003-1208-0936;
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AR 89

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Martins, IBA
Francisco, MR
Santos, MB
de Melo, NR

AF Miguel Landim, Ana Paula
Bernardo, Cristiany Oliveira
Araujo Martins, Inayara Beatriz
Francisco, Michele Rodrigues
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TI Sustainability concerning food packaging in Brazil

SO POLIMEROS-CIENCIA E TECNOLOGIA

RI Santos, Monique/ABF-6664-2020

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PY 2016

VL 26

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Fuinhas, JA

AF Pais, Daniel Francisco
Marques, Antonio Cardoso
Fuinhas, Jose Alberto

TI Drivers of a new dietary transition towards a sustainable and
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SO CLEANER AND RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION

RI Fuinhas, Jose Alberto/P-1603-2017; Marques, Antonio Cardoso/
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OI Fuinhas, Jose Alberto/0000-0002-6937-5420; Marques, Antonio
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Gonera, A
Myhrer, KS
Fifi, V
Valentin, D

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Arvisenet, Gaelle
Gonera, Antje
Myhrer, Kristine S.
Fifi, Viridiana
Valentin, Dominique

TI Meat replacer? No thanks! The clash between naturalness and processing:

An explorative study of the perception of plant-based foods

S0 APPETITE

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OI Gonera, Antje/0000-0002-7102-2472; Arvisenet,
Gaelle/0000-0001-7994-5610; Myhrer, Kristine
Svartebekk/0000-0002-3075-0799; Varela Tomasco,
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EI 1095-8304

PD FEB 1

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Sargolini, Massimo

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Environments

S0 APPLIED SCIENCES-BASEL

OI Pierantozzi, Mariano/0000-0001-7296-9898; PIERANTONI,
ILENIA/0000-0002-1227-7889; sargolini, massimo/
0000-0002-4870-5638

EI 2076-3417

PD AUG

PY 2020

VL 10

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Bogason, S
Hubbard, C
Samoggia, A
Nguyen, V
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Saviolidis, Nina M.
Olafsdottir, Gudrun
Bogason, Sigurdur
Hubbard, Carmen
Samoggia, Antonella
Nguyen, Vinh
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TI Investigating and stimulating sustainable dairy consumption
behavior: An
exploratory study in Vietnam

SO SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION

SN 2352-5509

PD NOV

PY 2023

VL 42

BP 183

EP 195

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EA OCT 2023

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Wang, SJ
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Chen, HJ

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Tan, Chunping
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TI Drought Adaptation in the Ningxia Hui Autonomous Region, China:
Actions,

Planning, Pathways and Barriers

SO SUSTAINABILITY

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EI 2071-1050

PD NOV

PY 2015

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TI Country-specific food culture and scientific knowledge transfer events-Do they influence the purchasing behaviour of seafood products?

SO AQUACULTURE

RI Hoerterer, Christina/GXF-7124-2022

OI Hoerterer, Christina/0000-0001-5627-456X; Petereit, Jessica/0000-0002-6373-7857

SN 0044-8486

EI 1873-5622

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Phillips, JW

Staff, AB

Goss, A

Fogg-Rogers, L

Ellwood, MDF

AF Hobbs, Laura K.

Phillips, Josie W.

Staff, Amy B.

Goss, Amber

Fogg-Rogers, Laura

Ellwood, M. D. Farnon

TI PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT PROMOTES CONSUMER CHOICE IN FAVOUR OF SUSTAINABLE PALM

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SO JOURNAL OF OIL PALM RESEARCH
EI 1511-2780
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